

Rabindranath Tagore's Educational Thoughts and some Sporadic Thoughts on Non-Formal Education

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ABSTRACT : In the first half of twentieth century Rabindranath confronted with the-then British conventional education system. He strongly opposed to the colonial nature of the existing system and wanted to introduce his own concept which was based on *Brahmacharyashram* and which was mingled with ancient *Tapoban* education system of India. Through his various and tireless writings he preached and established his own education system. He also preached equivocally for the mother tongue as the medium of instruction throughout almost all level of education. According to him, complete education should be activity-oriented, curriculum-packed education. Education in between the lap of nature is more essential for man-making. He advocated for free non-formal education with moral values. He expressed his ideas of education through 'Ashramer Rup O Bikash' Prabandhamala. He liked ancient Vedic Indian education but wanted to practise that with real scientific outlook.

At the fag-end of his life he thought deeply and earnestly for nurturing mass education. He and his few close associates wrote some books and booklets for helping to spread out mass education in the remotest corners of the country. His missions for spreading mass education were to build an economically and socially prosperous nation.

Keywords : Educational thoughts, Rabindranath Tagore, Non-formal education.

Between 1905 and 1947 education in undivided Bengal was mainly controlled by British rule. Then there was mainly two types of education system-one was sponsored by Government and other was private. Tagore protested against the system and established Brahmacharyasram in Bolepore-Santiniketan in the year 1901. The idea of free schooling was

formulated in his mind from earlier days. He himself did not like the conventional type of school. His own experience was depicted in his short-stories like Ginni and in his childhood days' memories. So he devoted himself in free schooling ideas of oldest days Tapoban's education system.

During the period of anti-partition movement in Bengal, Tagore had devoted much thought to educational problems. Between 1905 and 1917 he published a dozen of essays— “Address to students” (1905) “Education Reforms” (1906), “Education Problem” (1906), “National School” (1906), “Tapoban” (1909) “Religious Instruction” (1911), “Education Act” (1912) “Goals and Education” (1912), “Female Education” (1915), “Medium of Instruction” (1915), “Controlling Students” (1915) etc.

He expressed his views on nature, goal and method of national education, usefulness or futility of English as the medium of instruction, necessity of education through mother tongue, defects of our procedures of instruction, ideal of national school, need of religious instruction, ideal of schooling in Santiniketan ashram, female education and universal education.

For an instance – “Elsewhere it is found that the state has the obligation to educate the country. Hence we do not find any miserly treatment to education in Europe, Japan and America. If anybody declares loudly from a pulpit that only in this poor country of ours access to education needs to be made difficult and expensive, his voice will sound more and more discordant as his voice will rise from high pitch to higher. Even if Lord Curzon himself swears to assert that mother’s breast milk should be made costly; we cannot believe that he has been spending sleepless nights because of his anxiety for the child.” (Shikshar Vahan, 1915, op.cit 639).

According to Tagore, the education is moreover the participation in manifold co-curricular activities, enjoying kinship in co-operative and corporate living, sharing the happiness, worries and anxieties of others, appreciating the true, the good and the beautiful all those diversely but definitely lead to the

awakening at the subtle sensibility of goodness. The mind directly or indirectly undergoes an unobtrusive and for the periods under open sky learning (free periods of learning) that reflects and reacts to experiences achieved in an apparently flimsy or casual manner, – but herein lies the wonder of wonders because the inner discipline that makes life significant and worth living is achieved through cultivation of the sense of goodness.

It is also noticable that Rabindranath did not start formal system of adult education in his Santiniketan but he had some ideas of non formal education. He started new type of rural education in Surul-Sriniketan. But today’s concept of adult education was formulated after independence. Adult education was dignified as social education. At the time of India’s Independence, the greatest problem of education was that there was no national education system.

Tagore devoted much anxious thoughts on these problems. His second instalment of writings on education during 1919 and 1936 were elegant testimony to this fact. During this period his writings included “Causes of Dissatisfaction” (1919), “Test of Education” (1919), “Education Co-operation” (1919), Unity of Education (1921), Form of University (1932), Spread of Education (1933), “Education and Culture” (1935), “Assimilation of Education” (1936), “Ashram Education” (1936), “Address to Students” (1936).

If one goes through these ten essays, one can find that Tagore had identified the problems of education and analysed the nature of crisis confronting the education system in post World War I India and he suggested some solutions. He repeatedly pleaded for instruction through mother tongue in every part of the country. His vision for education had a scientific outlook. He

himself was self-educated. He did not like the conventional type of education. He wrote the satirical prose "Totakahini" to show the defects of formal education system.

In the last phase of his life Tagore thought deeply about the non formal education of the masses. He proposed the *Lokasiksha Granthamala* for spreading knowledge to the remotest corner of the country. He said that all learning matters should be spread over to each individual of Bengal and it was the motto of this laborious task. "Generally most of the populations could not accept the costly and time-taken education through tough methods, so a least portion of population was enlightened through education. No country can progress with the vast burden of illiteracy. So we have to take such measures through which we can able to reduce our burden rapidly and profusely....." (Notice Lokasiksha Granthamala, Sept. 1937) (Translation from the original text by the author of this essay).

To these steps of Granthamala series Rabindranath wrote "Viswa Vidyaparichay", Pramatha Choudhury wrote 'Prachin Hindusthan', 'Prithvi Parichay' by Pramathanath Sengupta etc. Rabindranath wrote the notice (Vignapti) for the Granthamala – which was quoted just before-hand by the essay writer's translation because it was originally written in Bengali language.

Tagore once uttered his ideas in such a way – "From the beginning I tried to create an atmosphere which I considered to be more important than the class teaching. The atmosphere of nature's own beauty was there waiting for us from a time immemorial with her varied gifts of colours and dance, flowers and

fruits, with the joy of her mornings and the peace of her starry nights....."

I invited renowned artists from the city to live at the school; leaving them free to produce their own work which the boys and girls watch if they feel inclined"

(My Educational Mission – The Modern Review, June 1931, P621-623)

Those incidents of Tagore's life show that his keen desires for free emancipation and activity-oriented education which might help a child to be self reliant and truly or properly educated. In one of Tagore's letters to his friend L.K. Elmhirst can show the real picture. In 19th December, 1937 a letter to Elmhirst showed his real endeavour for education – "It is well known that the education, which is prevalent in our country is extremely meagre in the spread of its area and barren in its quality. Unfortunately this is all that is available for us and the artificial standard set up is proudly considered respectable. Outside the *bhadralogue* class pathetic in their struggle for fixing a university label on their name, there is a vast, obscure multitude who cannot even dream of such a costly ambition. With them we have our best opportunity if we know how to use it. There and there only can we be free to offer to our country the best kind of all round culture, not mutilated by official dictators. I have generally noticed that when the charitably minded, city-bred politicians talk of education for the village folk, they mean a little left-over in the bottom of their cup, after diluting it copiously. They are callously unmindful of the fact; that the kind and the amount of the food, that is needful for mental nourishment, must not be apportioned differently according to the social status of those that receive it."

If we heard Rabindranath's utterings carefully we can find present day's flavour in it also.

Rabindranath wrote so many thought-provoking writings on education and those Bengali and English writings established his missions for education of the country. Besides conventional Brahamcharya Vidyalaya or later known as Viswabharati or Sriniketan, Tagore also believed for non-formal adult education.

He always thought for mass education of the country because the progress of the country should not possible without proper education and conciousness.

In his "Rassiar Chithi" he told rightly of the mass progress of Rassia which was shown after the revolution. He also pointed out India's backwardness and miserable condition for the lack of social awareness and awakening.

Inspite of education sector Tagore also noted down the mass's social upliftment through co-operative movement. Self-reliance and economic freedom are the main keys to open the door of success. In Tagore's opinion non-rigid curriculum and open access education system is more urgent and effective for mass education or non-formal education. Tagore's liberal thinking and foresighted measures must be effective and efficient not for the present but for the future education also.

Conclusion

Rabindranath's ideas of education was solid and strong for building a national system of education. Through his profuse and various writings on education and relevant matters showed new ideas of indigenious education

system. Nevertheless his ideas and works were effective and fruitful for the nation but also they proved their scientific bases and furthest future.

Tagore was also inclined to spread mass education for healthy and prosperous nation. He did not establish any centre for non-formal education in his life-time but his utmost endeavour was shown by his writings and works of last phase of his life.

His works were effective for his time and in future also. His unfinished works and plans for education are also valuable in present days. They are most modern in shape but if we want to mould them in our present time we may change or alter them easily. Tagore thought sporadically for non-formal education but nowadays we must think properly and wholly for the betterment of our society. Tagore's untested plans and ideas may be tested in our present education system.

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